

TERNARY COMPOSITES POLYPROPYLENE/ELASTOMER/FILLER:
STRUCTURE AND ELASTIC PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

The phase structure of ternary composites isotactic polypropylene/EPDM elastomer/calcium carbonate or talc was studied with the aid of dynamic mechanical measurements and electron scanning microscopy. The data provided by both methods show that the encapsulation of the filler particles by incorporated elastomer is controlled by their surface treatment: the as-received fillers are much more encapsulated (up to 60%) than the surface-treated calcium carbonate. The tendency to encapsulation decreases with increasing particle size. The composites with elastomer inclusions and filler particles separated from each other presumably have higher interfacial energies than the composites with encapsulated filler particles, and may persist for kinetic reasons.

INTRODUCTION

The poor impact resistance of isotactic polypropylene at temperatures below its glass transition temperature (about -10°C) is generally improved by admixing 5 to 20 v% of an ethylene-propylene (EPR or EPDM) elastomer. On impact, the elastomer inclusions act as stress concentrators and initiate multiple crazing; plastic deformation and orientation of the PP matrix in the craze tips absorb mechanical energy without incurring macroscopic damage. On the other hand, however, the elastomer phase accounts for a decrease in stiffness and yield stress, resistance to creep,

etc. These deficiencies can partly be compensated for by incorporating a particulate filler [1-3] or short fibres [4]. Alternatively, the insufficient impact strength of PP composites can be improved by adding an incompatible elastomer.

In our previous papers [5,6] we presented apparently contradictory results on the mechanical properties of PP/EPDM/CaCO₃ composites, indicating that the ternary composites may assume two different phase structures: (i) filler particles and elastomer inclusions are separately embedded in the PP matrix and do not interact with each other; (ii) EPDM elastomer encapsulates filler particles and the composite inclusions are embedded in the PP matrix. Obviously, if the elastomer is given and mixing conditions are kept constant, three factors may influence the phase structure: (i) matrix; (ii) filler, (iii) surface treatment of the filler. The objective of this paper is to evaluate the effects of these factors by means of dynamic mechanical measurements and scanning electron microscopy, and to single out the factor controlling the phase structure.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Six series of PP/EPDM/CaCO₃ composites were prepared in which two matrices, two fillers, and two different surface qualities (of one filler) were combined. To encompass the effects of particle shape, two series of PP/EPDM/talc composites were prepared with two differing sorts of talc. In each series, the volume fractions of the elastomer and filler were the following: $v_e = 0.05, 0.1, 0.2$; $v_f = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3$.
 Isotactic polypropylene: Mosten 52492 (Chemopetrol, Czechoslovakia) or Tipplen H501 (TVK, Hungary). Melt index: 3 g/10 min (230°C/210 N); molecular masses: $M_n = 6.5$ or 3.1×10^4 ; $M_w = 3.8$ or 5.2×10^5 ; crystallinity 63 or 61%.
 EPDM elastomer: Buna AP 331 (Hüls, FRG).
 Ground calcium carbonate: Durcal 2 or Millicarb (Omya, Austria). Average particle size: 3.6 μm for both fillers; specific surface area: 3.3 or 2.2 m^2/g .
 Talc: Finntalc MO5 (Finminerals, Finland) or talc EK1 (Peoples Republic of China). Average particle size: 2.8 or 15 μm ; specific surface area: 8.4 or 3.9 m^2/g .
 Surface-treated Durcal: 0.3 w% of stearic acid and 0.3 w% or calcium stearate.

All components were simultaneously mixed in the Rheomix 600 mixing chamber of Rheocord EU (45 ml; 190°C; 40 rpm; 15 min). The plates 150 mm × 220 mm × 1 mm were compression moulded at 190°C (5 min; 6 MPa); cooling rate was 20 to 30°C/min. The dynamic mechanical measurements were carried out with the aid of a freely oscillating torsional pendulum. SEM micrographs were taken by JEOL JSM 35 on fracture surfaces produced at the liquid nitrogen temperature on notched samples. The fracture surfaces were etched with heptane for 1 minute to remove the EPDM elastomer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The temperature dependences of storage and loss shear moduli show two distinct relaxations at -10 and -62°C (Fig. 1) which correspond to the glass transitions of the PP matrix and the EPDM inclusions, respectively. We showed in our earlier paper [7,8] that the size of the -62°C loss peak of binary blends PP/EPDM was proportional to v_e . However, in ternary systems [8] PP/EPDM/PE, it was proportional to $(v_e + v_{PE}) \leq 0.45$. In accord with earlier SEM evidence [9], the results were explained by formation of composite spherical inclusions where PE forms the core encapsulated by the EPDM elastomer. Fig. 1 clearly indicates that the size of the elastomer glass transition peak is markedly but differently increased by incorporated fillers. Obviously, the larger the peak (and, simultaneously, the

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of the storage and loss shear moduli of PP/EPDM/CaCO₃ composites (composition in v%):
 1 80/20/0; 2 60/20/20 Durcal surface treated; 3 60/20/20 Durcal as-received; 4 60/20/20 Millicarb as-received

drop in storage modulus), the higher the percentage of the filler encapsulated by the elastomer.

Differences in the reinforcing effects of the fillers used are also reflected in the G' vs. v_f dependences at a constant v_e (Figs 2-5). To make the confrontation more comprehensive, the experimental data are plotted along with the theoretical prediction rendered by the Kerner-Nielsen equation [10]:

$$G_c = G_m \frac{1 - \psi_e B_e v_e}{1 + A_e B_e v_e} \frac{1 + A_f B_f v_f}{1 - \psi_f B_f v_f}, \quad (1)$$

where indexes m, e and f denote respectively the matrix, elastomer and filler, $G_m = 0.79$ GPa is the matrix modulus (at 20°C),

$A_e = (8 - 10v_m)/(7 - 5v_m) = 0.938$ for the matrix Poisson ratio $v_m = 0.27$,

$B_e = [(G_m/G_e) - 1]/[(G_m/G_e) + A_e] = 0.997$ for the elastomer modulus $G_e = 1$ MPa,

$\psi_e = 1 + [(1 - P_e)/P_e^2]v_e$ is the correction function taking into account the maximum packing fraction of the inclusions $P_e = 0.70$,

$A_f = (7 - 5v_{me})/(8 - 10v_{me})$ for the binary matrix consisting of PP and EPDM (hence the index me),

$= (2.5/P_f') - 1$ if filler makes agglomerates in which the filler volume fraction is P_f' ,

$= 2x$ (aspect ratio of platelets)

Figure 2. The effect of the volume fraction of as-received Millicarb on the shear modulus of ternary composites
 Solid lines: theoretical prediction for the elastomer fractions v_e indicated ($A_f = 1.066$ for both matrices)
 Experimental data: \circ $v_e = 0$; \bullet 0.05; \bullet 0.1; \bullet 0.2

Figure 3. The effect of the volume fraction of as-received Durcal on the shear modulus of ternary composites
 Symbols as in Figure 2 ($A_f = 2.50$ for Mosten and 1.50 for Tipplen)

$$B_f = [(G_f/G_{me}) - 1] / [(G_f/G_{me}) + A_f] ,$$

$$\psi_f = 1 + [(1 - P_f) / P_f^2] v_f ,$$

While the parameters A_e , B_e , ψ_e were taken from our previous paper [7] on binary blends PP/EPDM, A_f was adjusted for Equation (1) to fit the experimental data for binary composites PP/filler ($v_e = 0$). As P_f of the fillers were not known, we uniquely assumed $P_f = 0.64$ characterizing the the random close packing of single-size spheres [10], though polydisperse fillers may be presumably packed even more densely. Possible variations of P_f , say, in the range 0.6 to 0.7 are not significant for the calculated G ,

Figure 4. The effect of the volume fraction of surface-treated Durcal on the shear modulus of ternary composites
 Symbols as in Figure 2 ($A_f = 2.50$ for Mosten and 1.50 for Tipplen)

Figure 5. The effect of the volume fraction of as-received talc EK1 (left) or Finntalc M05 (right) on the shear modulus of ternary composites
Symbols as in Figure 2 ($A_f = 11$ for Mosten/EK1 and 21 for Tipplen/Finntalc)

because for $v_f \leq P_f/2$ the correction function will vary only slightly. The shear moduli of calcium carbonate and talc were approximated [11] by 11 and 8 GPa, respectively. The parameters thus obtained for binary systems were inserted into Equation (1) to calculate the modulus of ternary composites. This procedure inherently assumes independent effects of the incorporated filler and elastomer on the composite stiffness.

TABLE 1

Apparent volume fraction of the elastomer, v_{ea} , in ternary composites PP/EPDM/filler

incorporated		v_{ea} , Mosten matrix				v_{ea} , Tipplen matrix			
v_e^a	v_f^b	Dt ^c	D ^d	M ^e	T ^f	Dt ^c	D ^d	M ^e	T ^g
0.05	0.3	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.12	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.07
0.1	0.1	0.1	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.1	0.11	0.13	0.12
0.1	0.2	0.1	0.13	0.11	0.17	0.1	0.12	0.14	0.13
0.1	0.3	0.12	0.14	0.12	0.18	0.1	0.15	0.17	0.16
0.2	0.1	0.2	0.21	0.23	0.22	0.2	0.26	0.27	0.25
0.2	0.2	0.21	0.26	0.29	0.27	0.21	0.29	0.30	0.28
0.2	0.3	0.25	0.30	0.31	0.30	0.22	0.37	0.35	0.30

^a volume fraction of the elastomer in composites; ^b volume fraction of the filler in composites; ^c Durcal treated; ^d Durcal as-received; ^e Millicarb as-received; ^f talc EK1; ^g Finntalc M05

Figs 2-5 show that only the surface-treated Durcal increases the modulus of ternary composites almost in accord with Equation (1). The as-received Durcal and Millicarb are much less effective; for $v_e = 0.2$, virtually no reinforcement can be detected with rising v_f . Though both species of talc raise G_c for all v_e used, the actual values are much lower than the predicted ones. To quantify the encapsulation and the differences between the fillers, the experimental data were inserted into Equation (1) and the apparent volume fraction of the elastomer, v_{ea} , was calculated (assuming that $v_e + v_f = v_{ea} + v_{fa}$). The results summarized in Table 1 show that the tendency to encapsulation is determined by the filler surface treatment. The type of PP matrix and of untreated filler play only a secondary role. (Slightly higher moduli of the Mosten/Durcal composites - compared to Tipplen/Durcal ones - may be due to some filler agglomeration. The reinforcing effect of Millicarb is lower, but identical in both matrices; $A_f = 1.066$ evidences good filler dispersion despite no surface treatment.) Neither the encapsulation of the untreated fillers by the incorporated elastomer, nor the separation of the surface-treated Durcal from the elastomer are quantitative. The amount of the untreated filler encapsulated at a constant v_e increases with v_f , achieving 50-60 v% of the incorporated filler.

The conclusions concerning filler encapsulation are corroborated by SEM micrographs (Figs 6 and 7). The particles of the as-received Durcal are more extensively encapsulated than the surface-treated particles (dark circular spots are imprints of the etched-off elastomer inclusions). Moreover, the tendency to encapsulation apparently decreases with increasing particle size. Talc particles (which are much bigger than Durcal particles) are mostly not embedded as a whole but partly covered by several spherical inclusions of the incorporated elastomer. Though the data in Table 1 indicate a similar overall encapsulation of calcium carbonate and talc, the detailed structures seem to be rather different.

The controlling effect of the surface treatment can be elucidated only tentatively on the basis of data obtained so far. In analogous ternary blends PP/EPDM/PE we observed [8] that PP and PE phases - either continuous or discontinuous - are always separated by an EPDM interlayer. An interpretation may be seen in that the phase structure with the interfaces PP/EPDM and EPDM/PE has a lower value of the Gibbs free energy than other conceivable structures, e.g. the PP matrix with separate PE and EPDM

a

b

Figure 6. Phase structure of the composites Tipplen (60 v%)/EPDM (20 v%)/CaCO₃ (20 v%): (a) as-received Durcal; (b) surface-treated Durcal. Scale bar 1 μm

a

b

Figure 7. Phase structure of the composites PP(60 v%)/elastomer (20 v%)/talc (20 v%): (a) Mosten/EPDM/EK1; (b) Tipplen/EPDM/Finntalc MO5. Scale bar 1 μm

inclusions. The surface energies (at 180°C) of PP and PE [12] are $\gamma_{PP} = 20.8$ and $\gamma_{PE} = 26.5$ mJ/m². The surface energy of EPDM can be estimated by means of the rule of mixtures [12]: $\gamma_{EPDM} = \gamma_{PE} x_{PE} + \gamma_{PP} x_{PP} = 24.3$ mJ/m², where $x_{PE} = 0.62$ and $x_{PP} = 0.38$ are mole fractions (the diene component is neglected). At room temperature, the values of 32.9, 38.7, and 32.6 mJ/m² are reported [13] for PP, PE and EPDM, respectively. Thus, it seems to be quite evident that the component with the intermediate surface energy forms the interlayer.

In the ternary composites PP/EPDM/CaCO₃, the sequence of components according to their surface energies remains the same, but the values for solid fillers are much higher [13]: as-received Durcal: 199; as-received Millicarb: 196; surface-treated Durcal: 149; Finntalc: 139 mJ/m². Thus, it may be expected that systems with encapsulated filler particles will be more stable and that encapsulation will take place irrespectively of the applied surface treatment. The experiments show, however, that the drop of the Durcal surface energy from 199 to 149 mJ/m² accounts for the preference of the phase structure with separated elastomer inclusions and filler particles. The key factor for this structural change seems to be the reduction of adhesion between filler and elastomer. Presumably, the conditions of mixing prevent the formation of a stable elastomer interlayer. A semiquantitative theory encompassing this effect has been developed recently [13], and further experiments on model ternary systems are under way.

CONCLUSIONS

The fillers without any surface treatment are more extensively encapsulated by the elastomer than the surface-treated filler (with lower surface energy). The encapsulation is not complete, achieving 50-60% of the incorporated filler; for a constant v_e , the amount of encapsulated filler increases with rising v_f . SEM micrographs reveal that the tendency to encapsulation decreases with increasing particle size. The systems with separated elastomer and filler presumably have higher interface energies than the systems with encapsulated filler particles. The former systems are less stable and probably persist due to kinetic reasons.

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